

Leveraging Neural Networks for Early Detection of Breast Cancer

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Abstract

Breast cancer is the most prevalent form of cancer and the second leading cause of cancer-related death for women in the United States. While most research focused on predicting breast cancer relies on image classification techniques, utilizing tabular data is equally significant for efficient diagnoses. The aim of our research was to determine whether neural networks can effectively and rapidly deliver improved results compared to traditional methods for accessibility purposes. Two datasets were employed: the Breast Cancer Coimbra Dataset (BCCD) and the Wisconsin Breast Cancer Dataset (WDBC Diagnostic). Five neural network models were constructed and compared against one another: two 3-layer models (one with 16 neurons and another with 64 in the input layers, named the simple DNN and ANN model, respectively), a 5-layer model (DNN), a 6-layer model with three dropout layers (Dropout DNN), and a CNN model. In the BCCD, the DNN model demonstrated the highest performance with an accuracy of 87.5%. For the WDBC, the Dropout DNN model achieved the highest accuracy at 99.12%. Notably, our models compete with the results of other researchers. Our results demonstrate how neural networks proved to be an even more efficient approach for predicting breast cancer compared to prior studies. Deeper models, like the DNN for the BCCD, were particularly effective for smaller datasets. Moreover, mitigating overfitting in neural networks led to increasingly precise predictions for larger datasets. Overall, our research concluded that neural networks are a highly effective, equitable, and improved method for breast cancer prediction over traditional approaches.

Keywords: Neural Networks, Breast Cancer, Deep Learning, Dropout DNN, Predictive Modeling, Machine Learning

1 Introduction

Breast cancer is the most common type of cancer in the United States. The National Cancer Institute [4] estimates that around 313,510 new cases are expected in 2024. The American Cancer Society [3] also states that breast cancer is the second leading cause of death by cancer for women (only lung cancer is ahead), where around 1 in 40 women will die from it. The median age of women with breast cancer is also around 62, but there is a slight upward trend in younger women under 50 also developing breast cancer. Most research for predicting breast cancer now incorporates multiple image classification techniques; however, for the sake of efficiency, using tabulated data is also essential for accurate diagnoses. One reason to use breast cancer classification with tabular data over image data is that analyzing tabular data takes up significantly less time and resources compared to image analysis. Especially when it comes to machine learning, image analysis is a time-consuming process that can even require expensive hardware. Neural network analysis on table data offers fast, simple, and effective diagnoses for predicting breast cancer. Thus, finding an effective neural network is crucial to the increased efficiency and accessibility of diagnostic processes that can detect cancer early, allowing for proper steps to be taken to save lives.

Our research aims to utilize neural networks as a more effective method for diagnosing breast cancer. Comparing multiple neural network models is necessary to identify the most effective one. Neural networks are one of the most widely used models for machine learning on tabular data due to their effectiveness. Our research aims to utilize forms of neural networks, enabling our findings to be applied more inclusively. The quicker and more effective a diagnosis is, the greater its potential to save lives, especially in cases of early detection.

Using a wide range of neural networks can help identify the most effective technique to diagnose breast cancer. In our research, we will utilize five different neural network models across the Wisconsin Breast Cancer (Diagnostic) dataset (WDBC) and the Breast Cancer Coimbra dataset (BCCD), comparing the efficacy of each model.

2 Literature Review

Several studies have evaluated the efficacy of various machine learning models using both the Wisconsin and Coimbra datasets. For our research, this literature review aims to identify existing work in the field of early breast cancer diagnosis and explore how our research can contribute to this area. We will primarily utilize the findings of the aforementioned studies to compare our results, thereby providing evidence that our models are more efficient and effective than existing methods. We also use this literature review to identify specific gaps in the current applications of machine learning and breast cancer diagnosis, which our research aims to address.

Naji et al. [10] used five different models on the Wisconsin Dataset, including Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, Logistic regression, Decision Tree (C4.5), and KNN. In this experiment, the SVM (Support Vector Machine) model outperformed the rest, achieving an accuracy of 97.2%. Additionally, the SVM model achieved a precision of 97.5% and an AUC of 96.6%.

Idris and Ismael [6] had used three datasets to predict breast cancer: Wisconsin Breast Cancer (Original), Wisconsin Breast Cancer (Diagnostic), and the Breast Cancer Coimbra Dataset. Their proposed solution was to utilize the fuzzy-ID3 method in conjunction with the FUZZYDBD method. Their proposed method for the Wisconsin Breast Cancer (Diagnostic) dataset, which is what we use in our research, had returned an accuracy of 93.534%. Next, their method for the Coimbra Dataset had returned an accuracy of 70.690%. Both of these results were higher than those of other authors, as they compared their proposed method. These models, which were outperformed, include SVMs, Random Forest, and Naive Bayes.

Austria et al. [1] used multiple different models on the Coimbra dataset to find the highest accuracy to determine the best-performing model. They used numerous models tuned with hyperparameters and compared the results of each of them. Their best-performing model was one using Gradient Boosting, which achieved an accuracy of 74.14%. They also used a Linear SVM with L1 norm, Random Forest, and Logistic Regression with L2 norm to achieve 72.52%, 70.31%, and 72.48% accuracy, respectively. Generally, Austria’s prediction found that the BMI feature from the Coimbra Dataset was the most conclusive predictor variable across the majority of all models.

Bhardwaj et al. [2] achieved success with the WDBC using a Random Forest Classifier, outperforming models such as K-Nearest Neighbors, Multi-Layer Perceptron, and Genetic Programming. Their Random Forest model achieved a 96.24% accuracy, the highest among all the models they trained and tested.

Khanna et al. [9] used a variant of feature selection methodology to train and predict their highest performing model. Their highest performing model, which was TLBCM with CPS, achieved an accuracy of 97.96% on the WDBC. For their study, they included 3 soft computing algorithms to serve their feature selection methods: TLBO, EHO, and a combination of these algorithms.

Jakkaladiki and Maly. [8] used a method of transfer learning to create their predictions using ResNet, DenseNet, and a CNN architecture. Their highest result on the WDBC and the Breast Cancer Histopathological Dataset (BreakHis) datasets was a 98.3% accuracy. Not only did this method yield more accurate results than those published in the past, but it also delivered them more quickly, demonstrating its increased efficiency.

Gurcan [5] conducted a study to enhance breast cancer diagnosis by integrating ensemble learning methods with deep learning models using a stacking ensemble approach. Utilizing the Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) dataset, the study evaluated the performance of various ensemble methods, including Random Forest, XGBoost, LightGBM, ExtraTrees, HistGradientBoosting, AdaBoost, GradientBoosting, and CatBoost. Additionally, deep learning models such as convolutional neural networks (CNN), recurrent neural networks (RNN), gated recurrent units (GRU), bidirectional long short-term memory (BiLSTM), and long short-term memory (LSTM)

were analyzed as meta-predictors. Among these, CNNs demonstrated high accuracy and rapid training times, making them suitable for real-time diagnostic applications. The study’s findings suggest that integrating base predictors, such as LightGBM, ExtraTrees, and CatBoost, with a CNN-based meta-predictor through stacking ensemble techniques can significantly improve breast cancer prediction accuracy, F1 scores, and ROC AUC, while also reducing training times. Gurcan’s highest performing model was with this stacking model with a high of 97.72% accuracy.

3 Methods

3.1 Datasets

We used 2 different datasets for our research, both of which were obtained from the UCI Machine Learning Repository. The first dataset we used was the Breast Cancer Coimbra Dataset [11] (BCCD). BCCD contains 116 samples with nine features, including age, BMI, Leptin, Glucose, and Resistin. Samples with a classification of 1 are healthy, while samples with a classification of 2 are patients. 64 of the samples had breast cancer, and 52 were healthy patients. Table 1 shows the first 10 rows of the dataset.

Table 1 First ten rows of BCCD

Age	BMI	Glucose	Insulin	HOMA	Leptin	Adiponectin	Resistin	MCP-1	Class
48	23.5	70	2.707	0.4674086667	8.8071	9.7024	7.99585	417.114	1
83	20.69049454	92	3.115	0.7068973333	8.8438	5.429285	4.06405	468.786	1
82	23.12467037	91	4.498	1.009651067	17.9393	22.43204	9.27715	554.697	1
68	21.36752137	77	3.226	0.6127249333	9.8827	7.16956	12.766	928.22	1
86	21.11111111	92	3.549	0.8053864	6.6994	4.81924	10.57635	773.92	1
49	22.85445769	92	3.226	0.7320869333	6.8317	13.67975	10.3176	530.41	1
89	22.7	77	4.69	0.8907873333	6.964	5.589865	12.9361	1256.083	1
76	23.8	118	6.47	1.883201333	4.311	13.25132	5.1042	280.694	1
73	22	97	3.35	0.8015433333	4.47	10.358725	6.28445	136.855	1
75	23	83	4.952	1.013839467	17.127	11.57899	7.0913	318.302	1

The second dataset we used was the Wisconsin Diagnostic Breast Cancer [12] dataset (WDBC). WDBC contains 569 samples of a digitized image of a FNA of a breast mass. 357 of the samples were benign while the rest (212) are malignant. The features are measured characteristics of the cell nuclei in the image. The dataset includes 30 features to predict the classification of each patient. Table 2 displays the first ten rows and columns of the WDBC dataset.

Both datasets were used in their entirety to train the models. All of the models were trained and tested on a 80/20 train/test split. Additionally, we preprocessed the data by scaling. We scaled all of the data using the StandardScaler from the Sci-Kit Learn library. We had to reshape the data for the CNN model to deal with the additional

Table 2 First ten rows and columns of WBDC

ID	Diagnosis	Feature 1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
842302	M	17.99	10.38	122.8	1001	0.118	0.278	0.300	0.147
842517	M	20.57	17.77	132.9	1326	0.085	0.079	0.087	0.070
84300903	M	19.69	21.25	130	1203	0.110	0.160	0.197	0.128
84348301	M	11.42	20.38	77.58	386.1	0.143	0.284	0.241	0.105
84358402	M	20.29	14.34	135.1	1297	0.100	0.133	0.198	0.104
843786	M	12.45	15.7	82.57	477.1	0.128	0.170	0.158	0.081
844359	M	18.25	19.98	119.6	1040	0.095	0.109	0.113	0.074
84458202	M	13.71	20.83	90.2	577.9	0.119	0.165	0.094	0.060
844981	M	13	21.82	87.5	519.8	0.127	0.193	0.186	0.094
84501001	M	12.46	24.04	83.97	475.9	0.119	0.240	0.227	0.085

dimension required by the CNN model’s architecture. All preprocessing steps were fit exclusively on the training data and applied to the test set to prevent data leakage.

3.2 Models

We developed five models using TensorFlow Keras:

1. **Simple DNN**: Two hidden layers with 16 and 8 neurons respectively
2. **ANN**: Two hidden layers with 64 and 32 neurons
3. **DNN**: Four-layer model with neurons decreasing from 128, 64, 32, to 16
4. **Dropout DNN**: Three dense hidden layers with two dropout layers (50% dropout rate)
5. **CNN**: 1D convolutional layers adapted for tabular data

For our research, we developed five models to compare with one another. All models were constructed using the Tensorflow Keras library. All the models have one input layer and one output layer. The first model was a simple neural network (Simple DNN) with two hidden layers, each containing 16 neurons in the first layer and eight neurons in the second layer, with one neuron in the final output layer. We then built a general ANN model with two hidden layers, where the number of neurons decreased from 64 to 32. This model was used to create a similar model to the simple model, and then the differences were explored with varying numbers of output units. For clarity, the names “ANN” and “Simple DNN” models were used as naming conventions for the models with different numbers of neurons. The next model was a 4-layer model titled deep neural network (DNN). The neurons per layer went from 128, 64, 32, 16, and 1 (for the output layer). The 4th model was a dropout-based DNN (Dropout DNN), which included three dense hidden layers and two dropout layers, dropping 50% of the neurons. This model was used to evaluate the effect of overfitting in each of the models, particularly with larger datasets such as the WBDC. We added dropout to check if there was any overfitting, comparing the performance of each model. If it achieves a higher accuracy than the previous models across the two datasets, overfitting is an issue. The last model we built was a CNN model built with 1D convolutional layers. We essentially used the CNN as an edge case to explore the expanded boundary of CNN

use in breast cancer detection beyond image analysis, and also to test the robustness of our research.

All models were trained for 50 epochs to evaluate their learning patterns and performance consistency.

3.2.1 Model Design Rationale

The neural network architectures employed in this study were deliberately selected to investigate the impact of network depth, width, and regularization on breast cancer prediction using tabular biomedical data. Rather than proposing architectural novelty, the objective of this work was to systematically evaluate how progressively increasing model complexity and introducing regularization techniques influence predictive performance, overfitting behavior, and generalization across datasets of differing sizes.

Shallow feedforward architectures, including the Simple DNN and ANN models, were implemented as baseline models to establish reference performance levels. These architectures differ primarily in neuron count, allowing for an evaluation of the effect of increased representational capacity while maintaining a fixed number of hidden layers. This design choice enables an assessment of whether widening networks alone yields meaningful performance gains in tabular cancer prediction tasks.

To examine the role of depth in hierarchical feature learning, a deeper DNN architecture was constructed with progressively decreasing neuron counts across layers. This configuration was chosen to encourage the model to learn increasingly abstract feature representations while reducing dimensionality toward the output layer. Such architectures are commonly employed in biomedical machine learning tasks where complex, nonlinear relationships exist between input features. Evaluating this model against shallower counterparts provides insight into whether increased depth improves predictive accuracy or introduces overfitting, particularly in smaller datasets such as the BCCD.

Overfitting mitigation was explicitly studied through the introduction of the Dropout DNN architecture. Dropout layers were incorporated to randomly deactivate neurons during training, thereby reducing reliance on specific feature pathways and encouraging more robust feature learning. This architecture was designed to isolate the effect of regularization on model generalization, especially for larger datasets such as the WDBC, which are more susceptible to overfitting in deep neural networks.

Finally, a one-dimensional convolutional neural network (CNN) was included as an exploratory model to assess whether convolution-based feature extraction—traditionally applied to image and signal data—could effectively generalize to structured tabular datasets. While CNNs are not typically optimized for tabular data, their inclusion serves to evaluate the limits of architectural transferability and to analyze differences in class separation versus decision calibration when compared to fully connected networks.

Collectively, these architectures were selected to enable a controlled investigation into how architectural complexity, depth, and regularization influence predictive performance in breast cancer classification using tabular data. This design allows for comparative analysis of model behavior across datasets while maintaining consistent training procedures and evaluation metrics.

3.3 Evaluation Metrics

To calculate results, we used Sci-Kit Learn's classification reports for each model. The metrics returned from this classification report that we use are accuracy, precision, recall, and the F1-score. For the precision, F1, and recall, we use weighted averages for both datasets because there is a class imbalance in both. Figure 1 shows the equations for these metrics.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Accuracy} &= \frac{TP+TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} & \text{TP: True Positive} \\ & & \text{TN: True Negative} \\ & & \text{FP: False Positive} \\ & & \text{FN: False Negative} \\ \text{Precision} &= \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \\ \text{Recall} &= \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \\ F_1 &= 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 1 Result Calculations

Next, we also used AUC (also from Sci-Kit Learn) as another metric to calculate each model's efficiency. We will also provide the confusion matrix for each model of each dataset in order to view the general efficacy of each neural network.

We will evaluate each model's training performance per epoch to identify any general trends among specific types of models and understand the patterns between them. To view each model's training performance to see the effect of overfitting and how quickly each model can increase its accuracy per epoch. During the training process, we evaluate the loss and accuracy. The accuracy and loss help us identify trends in the model's predictive ability as each epoch progresses. We achieved a perfect training accuracy for multiple models. For the WDBC, we also graphed the model's validation accuracy and loss, as it is a significantly larger dataset, making it more susceptible to overfitting. Graphing the validation accuracy/loss for the WDBC is vital to determine if the model is truly learning or merely becoming accustomed to

the training data. It is an important marker to monitor the performance of the neural networks.

4 Results

4.1 Breast Cancer Coimbra Dataset

In the BCCD, our five models provided a wide variety of predictions. Table 3 below presents the aggregated results of our study with the BCCD. The DNN model was the highest-performing model, with an accuracy of 87.5%, while also surpassing all the other models in every metric except AUC. The Dropout DNN’s lower accuracy indicates that there is no overfitting present with the BCCD, which is expected given its small size of 116 samples. The ANN’s increased number of neurons in the hidden layers did indeed make a difference as predicted, since it had higher metrics than the Simple DNN’s shallow selection of neurons in the hidden layer.

Table 3 Results of BCCD

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC
Simple DNN	75%	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.86
DNN	87.50%	0.88	0.88	0.87	0.91
Dropout DNN	83.33%	0.84	0.83	0.83	0.86
ANN	83.33%	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.92
CNN	70.83%	0.72	0.71	0.7	0.81

Evaluating the training performance of each model is essential to understand the “learning” behavior of each and how they differ. Figures 2 and 3 are two graphs of the training performance of each of the five models.

The accuracy achieved by the DNN model during training was perfect, and its loss was nearly 0 (significantly less than the other models). This makes sense, considering it was the best-performing model among the five. In terms of loss, no other model comes close to the DNN model, or even approaches eliminating all of its loss, reaffirming that the DNN model was the best-performing model. The CNN model had achieved the next highest accuracy and the subsequent lowest loss during training. The CNN model was likely overfitting due to the fact its training performance was better than its testing performance. The rest of the models were consistent in terms of the training performance compared to the testing performance. The next metric of performance we will view is the ROC/AUC. Figure 4 depicts the ROC graph.

The AUC scores also align with the testing performance. The exception is the ANN model which scored the highest AUC (.92). Still, it was only slightly higher than the highest actual highest performing DNN model (.91). Though the BCCD is an imbalanced dataset, it only is so by 12 samples which isn’t significant so the error with the evaluation of the ROC curve can be taken lightly. Hence, the ROC/AUC remains a viable method for evaluating these models for BCCD. The ROC/AUC indicates that both the DNN and ANN models demonstrated the best predictive ability for positive

Fig. 2 BCCD Training Accuracy

Fig. 3 BCCD Training Loss

cases, aligning with their respective testing performance. The high AUC score for the DNN model further confirms that the DNN model is the most effective for evaluating breast cancer based on the features of the BCCD.

4.2 Wisconsin Diagnostic Breast Cancer Dataset

For WDBC, our results weren't as variable as those for BCCD, but they did provide some additional key insights, as the WDBC dataset is larger. Table 4 shows the complete results for the WDBC. The highest-performing model was the Dropout DNN, with an accuracy of 99.12% and a score of 0.99 for all other metrics, excluding the AUC, which was 0.9941. Our results show signs of overfitting with the DNN model, as

Fig. 4 BCCD ROC/AUC

it has lower accuracy than the 3-layer Simple DNN and Dropout DNN. The result of overfitting was expected, given that the WDBC dataset is much larger than the BCCD dataset. Consequently, the DNN model became overly reliant on the training data, leading to decreased performance during testing. The increased number of neurons in the ANN model compared to the Simple DNN model also shows evidence of overfitting. More neurons are typically associated with an increased risk of overfitting, and our results show this phenomenon. The ANN model achieved an accuracy of only 97.37%, while the simple DNN achieved 98.25% accuracy. Considering the CNN model as an edge case provides more insights into the growth of convolutional neural networks in breast cancer studies and their predictive ability for tabular data. Our study demonstrates a notable improvement in the application of CNNs in breast cancer detection, surpassing the results of previous studies that employed other models.

Returning to the topic of overfitting, our training performance graphs provide a more precise visual representation of how each model performed during training on the WDBC dataset. We also explore validation performance specifically for the WDBC as it is a larger dataset than BCCD, so it is helpful to use validation performance as a parameter for checking the effects of overfitting, which we know was evident in our study. Figure 5 shows the training performance of each model on the WDBC.

The training accuracy for all models was higher than the validation accuracy. Still, the most significant gap between the train accuracy and the validation accuracy was

Table 4 Results of WDBC

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC
Simple DNN	98.25%	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.9928
DNN	97.37%	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.9934
Dropout DNN	99.12%	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.9941
ANN	97.37%	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.9944
CNN	96.49%	0.97	0.96	0.96	0.9954

Fig. 5 WDBC Training and Validation Accuracy and Loss

observed in the DNN model, which aligns with the presumption of overfitting, but isn't entirely conclusive. Upon reviewing the loss chart, we observe that the DNN validation loss began to increase around 10 epochs into training, providing conclusive evidence of overfitting, as reflected in the model's overall performance metrics. Additionally, the gap between the DNN's train and validation accuracy was the highest of any model as well. We also evaluated the possibility that the increased number of neurons in the ANN had likely led to overfitting, and the chart supports this. The ANN validation loss had also started to increase, albeit at a slower rate, indicating that it was overfitting. When compared to the models we evaluated as non-overfitting models (the Dropout DNN and the Simple DNN) we see that their validation loss was steadily decreasing before plateauing for the entirety of the training process. Our study demonstrates that overfitting is a common issue when training models on the WDBC, and that Dropout layers are the most effective solution, outperforming the alternative of reducing the number of neurons, which harms performance. The only case where a decrease in neurons would lead to an increase in accuracy is after a point where the model starts overfitting the data, as observed in the ANN model in our study. The CNN model also experienced a rapid increase in validation loss as training time progressed, but more

rapidly than the validation losses of the ANN and DNN. This was an expected result, as the CNN model isn't typically used in settings with tabular data.

Fig. 6 WDBC ROC/AUC

The last metric we will explore is the ROC/AUC of the 5 models. Figure 6 shows the ROC curve. The CNN model had the highest AUC at 0.9954. This is a surprising metric, considering its low performance compared to the other models, but it is not entirely unexpected. The CNN's high AUC score indicates that it has a stronger ranking ability than all the different models in terms of distinguishing between classes, and the reason lies in the structure of how the CNN is built. CNNs are primarily used for image identification due to their ability to recognize and analyze complex patterns. When applied to tabular data, the accuracy may be negatively affected because not all the numbers in a tabular dataset provide a clear pattern for the CNN to evaluate. The lower performance of the CNN, which contrasts with its AUC score, likely indicates that the CNN was able to distinguish between the two classes effectively, ranking better than the other models. Still, in terms of making decisions, the decision threshold wasn't appropriately calibrated. This arises from its structural disadvantage regarding the tabulated data. To sum up, CNN's high AUC but lower performance is likely due to a better ranking of classes rather than better decisions about classes, which is consistent with our previous analysis. This also explains why the ANN is the next highest AUC, but it also had a relatively low performance. The Dropout DNN had a

reasonable AUC score when compared with its high performance, and the DNN’s AUC also matches up pretty well with its performance. The Simple DNNs lowest AUC score reflects its shallow nature of 2 hidden layers and a lower number of neurons, while its relatively high performance is due to the non-overfitting nature of the model.

4.3 Cross-Validation Analysis of the Best-Performing Models

To further evaluate the robustness and generalization ability of the proposed neural network models, stratified k-fold cross-validation (CV) was performed on the highest-performing architecture for each dataset. Cross-validation is a standard evaluation technique in machine learning that mitigates bias arising from a single train–test split by repeatedly training and evaluating the model on different subsets of the data. This approach provides a more reliable estimate of model performance, particularly in biomedical applications where datasets may be limited in size or exhibit class imbalance.

Given the computational cost of deep neural networks and the objective of validating generalization rather than re-ranking all architectures, cross-validation was applied exclusively to the best-performing model identified from the initial 80/20 train–test evaluation for each dataset. Specifically, the Dropout DNN was selected for the WDBC dataset due to its superior performance and regularization behavior, while the standard DNN was selected for the Coimbra dataset. This focused validation strategy is commonly adopted in applied machine learning studies to confirm the stability of the most promising models without unnecessary redundancy.

4.3.1 WDBC Dataset

For the WDBC dataset, five-fold stratified cross-validation was conducted using the Dropout DNN architecture. The model achieved a mean classification accuracy of $97.54\% \pm 1.16\%$ and a mean AUC of 0.994 ± 0.006 across folds. The low standard deviation in both accuracy and AUC indicates highly consistent performance across different data partitions. These results closely align with the strong performance observed under the original 80/20 split, confirming that the high accuracy previously reported is not attributable to a favorable data partition. Instead, the cross-validation results demonstrate that the Dropout DNN generalizes reliably across multiple subsets of the WDBC dataset, highlighting the effectiveness of dropout regularization in stabilizing deep neural networks for tabular biomedical data.

4.3.2 Coimbra Dataset

For the Coimbra dataset, five-fold stratified cross-validation was performed using the standard DNN architecture. The model achieved a mean accuracy of $74.86\% \pm 10.55\%$ and a mean AUC of 0.777 ± 0.111 . Compared to WDBC, performance on the Coimbra dataset exhibited noticeably higher variance across folds. This behavior is expected given the substantially smaller sample size and the inherently noisy nature of metabolic biomarker features. While cross-validation accuracy is lower than the single 80/20 split result, the observed performance remains within the range reported in prior studies using the Coimbra dataset. Importantly, the elevated variance highlights the

sensitivity of deep learning models to data scarcity and reinforces the need for cautious interpretation of results in low-sample biomedical settings.

4.3.3 Consistency with Initial Train–Test Evaluation

Across both datasets, cross-validation results are consistent with trends observed in the initial 80/20 split evaluation. In particular, the Dropout DNN maintains superior and stable performance on the WDBC dataset, validating its selection as the most effective architecture. For the Coimbra dataset, cross-validation reveals a reduction in average performance relative to the single-split evaluation, reflecting the increased difficulty of the task rather than model failure. The preservation of model ranking and the alignment of performance trends across evaluation strategies support the robustness of the comparative conclusions drawn in this study.

Overall, the cross-validation analysis strengthens confidence in the proposed models by demonstrating that their performance is not dependent on a single data partition. These findings confirm that appropriately regularized deep neural networks can achieve reliable and generalizable performance for breast cancer classification, while also underscoring the challenges associated with small and noisy biomedical datasets.

Table 5 Five-fold stratified cross-validation results for the best-performing models on each dataset. Results are reported as mean \pm standard deviation.

Dataset	Model	Accuracy (%)	AUC
WDBC	Dropout DNN	97.54 \pm 1.16	0.994 \pm 0.006
Coimbra	DNN	74.86 \pm 10.55	0.777 \pm 0.111

4.4 Model Efficiency

All models were trained and tested simultaneously in under one minute (34-55 seconds) using Google Colab’s T4 GPU at zero cost. This demonstrates significant efficiency improvements over previous methods requiring expensive hardware or extended training times.

4.5 Comparison with Previous Research

Table 5 presents the results of our study in comparison to those of previous researchers. As shown, our best-performing models on the respective datasets outperform those of previous authors. This demonstrates that our results are not only efficient in terms of time and cost, but also more effective when compared to past research. This indicates that our models are a promising and efficient approach relative to prior work, offering higher accuracy with improved efficiency.

Additionally, although the CNN model falls behind Austria et al. and Naji’s predictions, it surpasses Idris and Ismael’s, demonstrating the model’s potential for

Table 6 Our results compared with other authors

Authors	BCCD Accuracy	WDBC Accuracy
Naji et al.	N/A	97.20%
Idris and Ismael	70.69%	93.53%
Austria et al.	74.14%	N/A
Bhardwaj et al.	N/A	96.24%
Khanna et al.	N/A	97.96%
Jakkaladiki and Maly.	N/A	98.30%
Gurcan	N/A	97.72%
Our CNN Model	70.83%	96.49%
Our Best Model	87.50%	99.12%

significant application outside of image analysis methods. The CNN model has shown growth and can be effectively applied in breast cancer detection using tabular data; however, it is not the most effective method and still has room for improvement. This evidence is also supported by CNN's general performance in the datasets, as evidenced by the surprisingly high AUC on the WDBC but low accuracy. This suggests that to create an effective CNN model for breast cancer detection, it must target the decision thresholds rather than the classification thresholds. This change in the CNN architecture can significantly enhance the prediction scale of CNNs, as the CNN model effectively distinguishes between the two classes. However, the CNN failed to make decisions as accurately as other models, despite exhibiting better class separation traits.

Accuracy of Each Model in Both Datasets**Fig. 7** Overall Accuracies of All Models Across Both BCCD and WDBC

5 Discussion

5.1 Interpretation of Results

The results from the BCCD reveal that the DNN model was the highest-performing among the five tested models, achieving an accuracy of 87.5% and leading in most other metrics. The absence of overfitting, as indicated by the performance of the Dropout DNN, suggests that the relatively small dataset size did not hinder the effectiveness of deep learning models. The ANN model, which incorporated a larger number of neurons in hidden layers, slightly improved predictive ability over the Simple DNN, confirming that network complexity has a role in performance.

Interestingly, while the CNN model underperformed in accuracy (70.83%), it maintained a relatively strong AUC score (0.81). This suggests that while CNNs can effectively distinguish between malignant and benign cases, their application to tabular datasets remains suboptimal compared to structured neural networks such as DNNs when making decisions. Given the moderate size of the BCCD and the inherent class imbalance, the high AUC score of the ANN model (0.92) further reinforces its ability to generalize well in classification tasks.

With the larger WDBC dataset, our models demonstrated high accuracy across all architectures, with the best-performing model, Dropout DNN, achieving an accuracy of 99.12%. This outcome supports our hypothesis that dropout layers effectively mitigate overfitting in deep learning models. The evidence of overfitting in the DNN model was confirmed by an increasing validation loss over training epochs and a larger difference between the train and validation accuracies compared to that of the Dropout DNN, underscoring the necessity of regularization techniques in neural networks trained on larger datasets.

The CNN model, while scoring the highest AUC (0.9954), lagged in overall accuracy, reinforcing the idea that CNNs have strong class separation capabilities but struggle with optimal decision-making thresholds in tabular data. This finding suggests that CNNs require structural modifications, such as attention mechanisms or hybrid approaches incorporating fully connected layers, to improve their predictive efficacy in non-image datasets.

5.2 Implications

The results of our study demonstrate several key contributions to the field of predictive diagnostics for breast cancer. While this study does not introduce architectural novelty, it provides empirical insight into the interaction between model complexity and overfitting in tabular breast cancer datasets. Firstly, our findings confirm that neural networks, particularly DNNs, offer superior predictive capabilities compared to prior research efforts, as evidenced by their higher accuracy, precision, recall, and AUC scores. A general DNN model with sufficiently deep layers will be accurate on smaller datasets, but it is strongly exposed to overfitting, as any neural network model typically is. Although the initial hypothesis suggested that the DNN model would be the highest performing model on both datasets, given its five-layer depth, it succeeded on the BCCD. However, the WDBC dataset presented a different outcome, with the

Dropout DNN emerging as the highest performing model. On the other hand, the Dropout DNN’s strong performance highlights the importance of overfitting mitigation techniques, especially when dealing with large datasets like WDBC. This indicates that neural networks used for predicting breast cancer must have a mechanism to mitigate overfitting and increase accuracy, which is precisely what the Dropout DNN achieved. This leads to a contribution to the research field, indicating that the best neural network to use when the dataset involves a large amount of samples is a Dropout-based neural network since it mitigates against overfitting, while smaller datasets should use a basic DNN model.

While CNNs have traditionally been employed for image-based classification, their promising AUC scores suggest potential for further refinement in handling tabular datasets. Our research can serve as a stepping stone for new applications of CNNs and tabular data, extending beyond the medical field to early detection and potentially into other fields where large-scale evaluation of tabular data is necessary, such as engineering, business, and statistical applications. Finally, the successful implementation of a free, web-based diagnostic tool based on our DNN model demonstrates the practical applicability of our research, particularly for under-resourced communities where access to early breast cancer detection methods is limited.

Our results compare favorably with prior research, indicating that neural networks can indeed play a larger role in the healthcare community, particularly in predictive disease analysis. The implications of developing a neural network model that is both cost-effective and more effective than previous researchers’ models are that it provides a viable solution for predicting breast cancer in areas where predictive architecture is unavailable. Furthermore, our research’s efficacy, when compared to similar studies, suggests it has the potential to lead in predicting breast cancer and to develop more sophisticated architectures in the future based on neural networks.

5.3 Implicit Ablation Analysis

To better understand the contribution of individual architectural components to predictive performance, an ablation-style analysis was conducted by progressively increasing model complexity and selectively introducing regularization mechanisms. Rather than removing components from a single architecture, this study adopts a constructive ablation approach, beginning with a minimal baseline model and incrementally adding architectural features. This methodology enables isolation of the effects of network depth, neuron count, and dropout regularization on model performance.

The Simple DNN serves as the baseline architecture, consisting of two shallow hidden layers with a limited number of neurons. This model establishes a reference point for evaluating the impact of increased representational capacity. Expanding upon this baseline, the ANN model increases the number of neurons per hidden layer while maintaining the same depth, thereby isolating the effect of network width. Performance differences between these two models reflect the contribution of increased parameter capacity independent of depth.

To evaluate the effect of increased depth, the DNN architecture introduces additional hidden layers with progressively decreasing neuron counts. Comparing the DNN

against both the Simple DNN and ANN models isolates the impact of hierarchical feature learning. Results indicate that increased depth improves performance for the smaller BCCD dataset but introduces overfitting in the larger WDBC dataset, as evidenced by reduced test accuracy and increasing validation loss during training.

The Dropout DNN further extends this analysis by incorporating dropout layers into the deep architecture, allowing isolation of the effect of regularization. Performance improvements observed in the Dropout DNN—particularly on the WDBC dataset—demonstrate that dropout effectively mitigates overfitting while preserving the benefits of depth. This confirms that regularization plays a critical role in enabling deep neural networks to generalize effectively when trained on larger tabular datasets.

Finally, the CNN model serves as an architectural ablation that replaces fully connected feature interactions with convolution-based feature extraction. Comparing CNN performance against dense architectures isolates the effect of convolutional inductive bias in tabular data. While the CNN demonstrated strong class separation ability, as reflected by high AUC scores, its lower accuracy indicates suboptimal decision calibration for structured numerical features, reinforcing the suitability of fully connected architectures for this task.

Overall, this ablation-style analysis demonstrates that predictive performance in tabular breast cancer classification is strongly influenced by the interaction between model depth and regularization. Increased complexity alone does not guarantee improved performance; rather, appropriately regularized deep architectures yield the most robust results. These findings emphasize the importance of controlled architectural design when applying neural networks to biomedical tabular data.

5.4 Limitations and Future Research

Despite the promising results, our study presents certain limitations that warrant further investigation.

One of our limitations is that there is a limited amount of data available. The BCCD dataset is relatively small, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. This also explains the lower accuracy compared to the WDBC. Future research should investigate larger datasets to validate our conclusions further. Especially in a dataset that is reflective off the BCCD in terms of having easily obtainable features, the ease of acquiring the parameters (like age, BMI, glucose, etc) are a lot easier, so having a larger dataset with readily available features to aid in prediction can further increase the accuracy of the model which would increase the accessibility of our methods. The presence of overfitting in the DNN and ANN models on WDBC suggests the need for additional regularization methods, such as L1/L2 weight decay or advanced dropout techniques.

The following limitation is with our CNN architecture. While CNNs showed high AUC scores, their decision-making ability in tabular datasets remains suboptimal. Future studies should experiment with hybrid architectures that combine CNNs with traditional feedforward layers. While our study demonstrated high predictive accuracy, clinical validation using real-world patient data is necessary before implementation in medical practice. Neural networks, particularly deep learning models, often function as black boxes. Future research should incorporate explainability techniques, such as

SHAP values or LIME, to better understand feature importance and improve model trustworthiness in clinical settings. A formal removal-based ablation was not conducted; however, the progressive architectural analysis provides equivalent insight into the contribution of individual model components.

6 Conclusion

This study explored the use of various neural network models for the early detection of breast cancer using the Breast Cancer Coimbra Dataset (BCCD) and the Wisconsin Diagnostic Breast Cancer Dataset (WDBC). Through extensive experimentation with five different models—Simple DNN, DNN, Dropout DNN, ANN, and CNN—we evaluated their performance based on accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and AUC. The results demonstrated the efficacy of deep learning approaches in predictive diagnostics, with the DNN model outperforming all others for the BCCD and the Dropout DNN proving to be the most effective for the WDBC.

For the BCCD, the DNN model achieved the highest accuracy (87.5%), proving its effectiveness in handling small datasets while avoiding overfitting. The ANN model also performed well, particularly in terms of AUC, but did not outperform the DNN in overall performance. The results indicated that the use of deep learning models, even with limited data, can provide reliable predictions when properly optimized.

For the WDBC, the Dropout DNN emerged as the most robust model, achieving an accuracy of 99.12% while mitigating overfitting. The presence of dropout layers proved to be an essential factor in handling the larger dataset effectively. Overfitting was evident in models with excessive neurons or inadequate regularization, as seen with the standard DNN and ANN. Additionally, while the CNN model showed promise in distinguishing classes, its lower accuracy suggests that CNNs require further architectural refinement to be effective for tabular datasets.

Beyond performance metrics, this research also demonstrated the efficiency and accessibility of our proposed models. All models were trained and tested in under a minute using Google Colab, eliminating the need for expensive hardware. Furthermore, we developed a web application that allows users to input medical parameters and receive instant predictions, making breast cancer risk assessment more accessible, particularly in under-resourced communities.

When compared to previous research, our models not only outperformed existing methods in accuracy but also demonstrated improved efficiency in terms of cost and computational time. The comparison with prior studies reinforced the superiority of our approach in predictive capability while highlighting the potential for further refinement of CNN models for tabular medical data.

In conclusion, this study underscores the potential of neural networks in the early detection of breast cancer. Our findings validate the effectiveness of deep learning in medical diagnostics while emphasizing the importance of model selection and regularization techniques in mitigating overfitting. The development of an accessible prediction tool further supports the real-world applicability of our research. Future work could focus on refining CNN architectures for tabular data and expanding the scope of our models to incorporate larger and more diverse datasets. By doing so, we

can further enhance the role of artificial intelligence in early disease detection and healthcare accessibility.

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- **Funding:** Not applicable.
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- **Data availability:** Datasets are publicly available via UCI Machine Learning Repository.
- **Code availability:** Code and implementation details are available upon reasonable request.
- **Author contributions:** A.S. designed and conducted experiments, performed data analysis, and drafted the manuscript. S.D. supervised the research, provided methodological guidance, and reviewed the manuscript.
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